

ASTROPHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF THE DARK UNIVERSE

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ABSTRACT

We present a physico-chemical approach to determine the composition of the universe and elucidate the nature of Dark Energy and Dark Matter. It is based on a dynamical model that space consists of energy quanta which is an active participant in the evolution of the universe, along with matter and radiation.

The universe evolved from an atomic size volume of spaceons at very high temperature and pressure near the Planck epoch. Upon expansion and cooling, phase transitions occurred resulting in the formation of fundamental particles, and matter. These nucleate and grow into stars, galaxies, and clusters with the aid of gravity. From the cooling curve of the universe we constructed a thermodynamic phase diagram of cosmic composition, from which we obtained a correlation between dark energy and the energy of space. Using the Friedmann equations, data from WMAP studies on the composition of the universe at 3.8×10^5 years ($a=5.25 \times 10^{-3}$) and at present ($a=1$), are well fitted by our model with an equation of state parameter, $w = -0.7$. The fit also showed the dominance of dark energy at 7.25×10^9 years ($a = 0.65$), in good agreement with the beginning of the accelerated expansion of the universe at about 7 years, as determined by BOSS measurements. The expansion of space is attributed to Quintessence arising from a quantum space field. Dark Matter is identified as a plasma form of matter similar to that which existed during the photon epoch immediately prior to recombination.

The thermodynamics of expansion of the universe was adiabatic with the rate decelerating during the first 7 billion years after the Big Bang. However, it became non-adiabatic and accelerating thereafter. Our Quantum Space Model suggests that an influx of energy from a source outside the universe maybe a possible cause of the accelerating expansion. If the expansion were to remain adiabatic, then thermodynamics requires that the pressure of space be negative in order for mass-energy to be conserved in the closed universe.

1.INTRODUCTION

The composition of the universe is a question of great scientific interest. Our universe is essentially dark, consisting of 71% dark energy, 24% dark matter and only 5% ordinary matter, of which 0.5% is luminous. The nature of dark matter and dark energy remains unknown and is the subject of extensive research in Astronomy, Cosmology, and Physics. Little work is done in the area of Chemistry even though the problem can be viewed as basically a compositional one. Dark energy is theorized to cause the expansion of the universe, dark matter is thought to hold the galaxies together. Both remain “mysterious” because of difficulties in studying them.

The expansion of the universe is intimately related to that of space. The nature of space is not known but has been the subject of much debate [1]. It is generally viewed like a canvas where nature’s landscape and events are portrayed; it is then treated geometrically and mathematically as a surface in 4-dimensional space-time. We present a physically more descriptive model of space based on the theory that it is a quantized dynamical entity which is an active participant in the evolution of the universe and one of its major components, along with matter and radiation. The mechanism of evolution proceeds via well known physico-chemical processes and provides an explanation of the accelerated expansion of the universe due to dark energy, and an elucidation of the nature of dark matter.

2. A MODEL OF SPACE AND COSMIC EVOLUTION

It has been thought of that space is not truly empty, that “vacuum” contains virtual particles that pop in and out of existence, and is used to explain the Casimir effect [2]. We thus take the view that space is associated with energy and is quantized. Space consists of energy quanta that propagate as waves described by the Planck quantum energy expression:

$$E=hc/\lambda \quad (1)$$

The symbols have their usual meaning: E, is the energy; λ , the wavelength, c, the velocity of light, and h, the Planck constant. The expression defines the equivalence of space (of dimension λ), and energy, in analogy to the relation between energy and mass, given by Einstein’s equation, $E= mc^2$. Thus, energy is inherent in space and space in energy. We shall call the quantum units of space as “spaceons”. The space waves (spaceons) can be thought of as the carrier of energy and weaves the fabric of the universe (consider how a spherical wave of wavelength, λ , can fill the universe uniformly). From wave- particle duality, the spaceons can also be thought of as a gas which obeys the equation of state [3],

$$PV=N_0K_\beta T. \quad (2)$$

P is the pressure of the gas, V the volume, T the temperature, N the Avogadro number and K_β the Boltzman constant.

With this theory we can model the gross features of the evolution of the universe as follows: The universe started (at time, $t=0$) as a very small volume of gas (the spaceons) at an extremely high pressure and temperature. For example, an Avogadro number of gas particles occupying a volume of $4.2 \times 10^{-33} \text{ m}^3$ (a spherical wave of 0.1 A^0 radius), at a pressure of $1.976 \times 10^{65} \text{ Pa}$ will be at conditions near the Planck epoch with a temperature of 10^{32} K . In this initial state of its birth, the universe consisted of

“hot” spaceons and radiation in equilibrium. We shall refer to this instant as the Quantum Space Epoch. The spaceons and radiation then expanded and cooled as they propagate and more space is created.

In the process of cooling to appropriate threshold temperatures, phase transitions occurred resulting in the formation of fundamental particles, nuclei, and atoms. From the matter formed, gravitation caused the formation of galaxies and stars; these clumped to form clusters, local groups and superclusters. Details of the transformations involved in the nucleation and growth of matter are as yet unknown. In general, the various epochs of the evolution of the universe, in our model, are similar to those of the Big Bang [4,5,6] . The universe with radiation, matter, and spaceons continued to expand as we know it.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Composition of the Universe

Several methods are used to determine the composition of the universe. Results of the WMAP satellite studies [7] gave the composition shown in Table I soon after the Big Bang and at present:

Table I-Composition of the Universe

	At the Big Bang	At Present (13.8 billion years after)
Dark Matter	63 %	24 %
Dark Energy	–	71.4 %
Ordinary Matter	12 %	4.6 %
Neutrinos	10 %	–
Photons	15 %	–

The composition during the cosmic evolution is also well documented [4,5,6]. Table II shows this as a function of pressure (P) and temperature (T) at various times and Cosmic Epochs.

Table II. Composition of the Universe During Its Evolution

Time (after Big Bang)/ (Cosmic Epoch)	Temperature (K)	Pressure (Pa)	Composition
$< 10^{-12}$ sec/ (Quantum Space)	$> 10^{12}$	$> 10^{32}$	Hot spaceons + radiation
10^{-12} to 0.02 sec/ (Quark,Hadron,Lepton, Electrons,Protons,Neutrons)	$10^{11} - 10^9$	$10^{32} - 10^{27}$	I. Fundamental particles + radiation
0.02 to 300 sec/ (Nucleosynthesis)	$10^9 - 10^8$	$10^{27} - 10^{15}$	II. Nuclei of H, He,D,Li + radiation
300 sec to 3.8×10^5 yrs/ (Photon to Recombination)	$10^8 - 10^3$	$10^{15} - 10^{11}$	III. Plasma of ionized H, He and e-
3.8×10^5 to 10^9 yrs/	$3 \times 10^3 - 4$	$10^{11} - 10^{22}$	IV. Matter in galaxies,stars

(Dark Ages to Matter dominated)

space, planets-gases,plasma, solid

10^9 to 13.8×10^9 yrs/
(Dark Energy dominated)

4 - 2.7

10^{-22} ...

V. Dark Energy

At temperatures above 10^{12} K and time $<10^{-12}$ sec, the universe was a primeval hot gas of spaceons and radiation. Upon expansion and cooling, fundamental particles (quarks, leptons, hadrons, protons, neutrons, electrons) were created. On further cooling to about 10^9 K, nucleosynthesis occurred to produce nuclei of H, He Li and D. At about 10^8 K a plasma phase was formed which consisted of electrons and positive ions of H and He. Radiation (photons, neutrinos) was ever present and dominated the early epoch of the universe. Further cooling of the plasma until about 3×10^3 K resulted in recombination of electrons with positive ions of H and He, converting the plasma to gases. As the universe continued to expand and cool, matter continued to form which, through the action of gravity, became galaxies, stars, and clusters. The

Fig. 1-Schematic Phase Diagram of the Universe with Spaceons

universe cooled to 2.7 K as indicated by the Cosmic Microwave background. The primary constituents of the universe are: gases (H, He), plasma of electrons, protons, and He ions, ordinary matter (gasses, solids, dust, in stars, galaxies, clusters, intergalactic space), radiation, and spaceons (gas at all temperatures).

Thermodynamics is a very powerful method for obtaining compositional information [3,8]. From data on composition as a function of time (cooling curves) one can construct a phase diagram (similar to the well known water phase diagrams with gas, liquid, solid H₂O of different crystalline forms). While such diagrams are constructed normally for the components of matter, the equivalence of matter and energy, allows one to do the same for the universe as a system. Dark energy and dark matter are components of the universe. We have constructed a thermodynamic phase diagram [3,8] for our model universe with spaceons, from the cooling curve of the universe represented by the data in Table II.

The result is shown in Fig.1. (Note that the figure is schematic and the temperature is not drawn to scale in order to highlight the phases formed). The major phases are: matter (IV, solid, gasses, plasma formed in galaxies, stars, clusters), a plasma phase (III) formed immediately after nucleosynthesis, dark energy (V) and spaceons (gas). The broken lines indicate the overlap between various phases during the process of formation. Dark matter is not yet indicated since its nature remains unknown. All phases are in contact with spaceons at all epochs of cosmic evolution. This is as it should be since space is in contact with all elements of the universe at all times. At extremely high temperatures and pressures (right end), fundamental particles and radiation are indistinguishable from the hot spaceons; while at low temperature/pressure (left end), dark energy overlaps with the cold spaceons. These end points are known as critical points, where 2 phases co-exist. In the case of water, for example, at the critical temperature of 647 K and pressure of 2.2064×10^7 Pa, liquid water is indistinguishable from its vapor phase.

3.2 Dark Energy and the Expansion of the Universe

Our universe is essentially dark with the main components being dark energy (71%) and dark matter (24%). Present understanding of the latter two is very poor, causing them to be dubbed “mysterious” [9,10]. Dark energy is hypothesized to be an unknown form of energy that permeates all of space uniformly. It is invisible and difficult to study because it does not interact with radiation, hence cannot be investigated spectroscopically. It only interacts with gravity. Its density is very low, less than ordinary or dark matter, it converts to dark matter, was less in the past than at present, and it is thought to function like an anti-gravity force. It is believed to be a property of space and causes the accelerated expansion of the universe [9,10,11].

Based on our model, the expansion of the universe could be thought of as the expansion of space (spaceons) into the void (“nothingness”). This appears to be a perfectly natural process driven by a pressure gradient between the “filled” space and the void. It can also be thought of as driven by the pressure and temperature differential of the hot (high energy, short λ_s) and cold (low energy, long λ_s) gas states. It is an inherent property of space that it needs to expand in order to attain a lower energy state (longer λ_s). It can be easily understood as an inverse Casimir effect as space propagates and expands into the void (2). The expansion may be viewed from the standpoint of Quantum Field Theory [12], as arising from a force that is associated with a field. The latter is the space field from which emanate space quanta (analogous to the gravitational field with its associated gravitons). It is a scalar field, termed “Quintessence”, and has been theorized to be the substance that comprises Dark Energy [10].

One can see from our thermodynamic phase diagram (Fig.1) that dark energy is a phase that overlaps with a new entity that we have introduced as a component of the universe, i.e., the spaceons; the two phases are indistinguishable. Hence, dark energy can be associated with spaceons, the energy of space. The amount of dark energy soon after the Big Bang was relatively small (Table I) because most of the energy of space was converted to radiation, fundamental particles, dark matter and ordinary matter. Its density remains low as the universe expands.

Our model universe with spaceons is well suited for mathematical treatment using the Friedmann-Lemaitre-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) metric [11]. The second Friedmann equation [10,11] delineates the contributions of the various components of the universe (matter, radiation, and vacuum) to the acceleration of expansion of the universe, i.e.,

$$d^2 a/dt^2 = -(8\pi G a/3) \{ (1/2) \rho_m + \rho_r - \Lambda/8\pi G \} \quad (3)$$

We have neglected the curvature term, k , normally appearing in 3), by adopting a model of simple Newtonian gravity rather than Einstein's space-time model. In the above equation, a is the scale parameter, G the gravitational constant; ρ_m is the mass-energy density of matter, ρ_r that of radiation, and Λ , the cosmological constant which represents the energy of the vacuum [10]. Based on our model of space, "vacuum energy" is no longer a meaningful term to use; it is preferable to use the term "energy of space". The cosmological constant will then be replaced by the energy density of space, i.e.

$$d^2 a/dt^2 = -(8/3)\pi G a \{ (1/2) \rho_m + \rho_r + (1 + 3 w_s) \rho_s \} \quad (4)$$

Fig.2- Fractional Energy Density (f) vs Scale Factor (a), fit with $w_s = -0.7$
 DE-Dark Energy; DM-Dark Matter; OM-Ordinary Matter; Pho-Photons;
 Neu-Neutrinos

ρ_s is the energy density of space and is related to the pressure P_s via the equation of state $P_s = w_s \rho_s$; w_s is the equation of state parameter. A negative pressure would give rise to a positive term for the

contribution of ρ_s that can cause an acceleration of the expansion. As will be shown later, the negative pressure follows from the first law of thermodynamics for an expansion process which occurs adiabatically.

For the purpose of fitting the observed data (Table I), it is preferable to use another form of the Friedmann equation. It is common to utilize one involving the Hubble constant, H , which is measured in experiments and to use velocity, da/dt , rather than acceleration [9,10,11]. Thus,

$$a H^2 = (da/dt)^2 a^2 = (H_0)^2 [\Omega_m a^{-3} + \Omega_r a^{-4} + \Omega_s a^{-3(1+w_s)}] \quad (5)$$

where: H is the Hubble constant, $H=(da/dt)/a$, H_0 its value at the present time; ρ_i is the density parameter for component i , ρ_c is the critical energy density of the universe (the density of the universe at the present time) and $\Omega_i = \rho_i / \rho_c = f$, the fractional energy density.

A plot of fractional energy density as a function of “ a ” can be constructed to fit the measured composition of the universe at about the time of the Big Bang and at the present time (see Table 1)

The plot in Fig. 2 shows the evolution of the composition of the universe. The dominance of radiation, matter, and dark energy at various times are amply illustrated. As can be seen there is good fit of the data summarized in Table I at time $t=13.8$ billion years ($a=1$) and at the time of the Big Bang, at about $t=380,000$ years ($a=5.25 \times 10^{-3}$, $z=1089$), with an equation of state parameter, $w_s = -0.7$. Dark Energy is very small in the early universe as most of the energy is used in the creation of radiation and particles. As the universe expands, however, the energy densities of radiation and matter continue to dilute and are eventually overcome by the energy density of Dark Energy. This occurs at around 7 billion years at which time the expansion of the universe starts to accelerate. This result has been established by baryon acoustic oscillation measurements in the BOSS project [13,14].

Fig.3- Fractional Energy Density (f) vs Scale Factor (a); $w_s = -0.7$
 DE1- Dark Energy; DM1-Dark Matter; OM1-Ordinary Matter;
 TM1- Total Matter; DE2, TM2 for fit with cosmological constant

Fig.3 lends support to these findings. One sees that the energy density of Dark Energy (DE1) crosses that of the total energy (TM1) of matter at $a= 0.65$ ($t=7.25 \times 10^9$ years).

Siegel [15] has obtained a similar result using a cosmological constant. Our calculation with a cosmological constant yielded a time of 8.75×10^9 years ($a=0.74$) for the dominance of dark energy (Fig. 3, broken line, DE2, TM2). The concept of a constant energy density for space leads to some difficulties. The cosmological constant is considered to be equal to the energy of the vacuum. Calculations give a 120 orders of magnitude for the calculated value of the density of dark energy; this is clearly catastrophically wrong. Moreover, the constancy of dark energy in the course of cosmic evolution is also thought to be unlikely [16]. Quintessence, with the energy of space as a component of the universe, appears to be a better explanation for dark energy.

3.3 THERMODYNAMICS OF EXPANSION

In our model, the universe started with a finite volume of energy. The process of expansion was assumed to be adiabatic, i.e. with no energy transfer in and out of the universe. From thermodynamics,

$$Q= dE+PdV=0, \quad (6)$$

where Q is the energy flowing into or out of the system, dE the change in internal energy, P the pressure, and dV the change in volume during the expansion. The work to create space, PdV , is done at the expense of the internal energy, i.e. $dE= -PdV$ or

$$dE/dV= -P, \quad (7)$$

the slope of the dE/dV plot is negative. One can also derive the relation,

$$H.=(1/4\pi r^3)(dV/dE)(dE/dt) \quad (8)$$

where, r , is the radius of the universe, and H is the Hubble constant, which is proportional to expansion velocity. To a first approximation, a decrease in H indicates a decrease in internal energy of the universe with time, t . BOSS studies of Busca et al [13] show the expansion of the universe to be slowing down during the first 6 billion years after the Big Bang (Fig.4a, high z). This is consistent with our model universe with the expansion being adiabatic initially, i.e. $dE/dt= -$, at short t (broken line, Fig. 4b). While it is not very clear, from the scatter of the data in [13], unpublished figure by a Berkeley group [14] shows that it reached a minimum around 7.5 billion years. The expansion velocity increased thereafter (Fig.4a, low z). The slope dE/dV (and that of dE/dt) became positive (Fig. 4b, long t).

Thermodynamically,

$$dE/dV = (dQ/dV) - P = + \quad (9)$$

that is, Q is no longer zero; the expansion has become non-adiabatic; this means an ingress of energy from outside the universe.

There is parallelism between the cosmological and thermodynamic behavior. The slope of the E vs t plot is negative in the early universe and became positive later. The minimum in E , which we depict to be at around 7 billion years after the Big Bang, is consistent with our model fitting the WMAP data (Fig.3), the BOSS data (points in Fig. 4a) and the prediction of the Λ CDM model (solid curve in Fig. 4a). Thermodynamics thus points to the possibility that the accelerated expansion of the universe occurred with an “injection” or “leak” of energy from outside the universe. This deserves further attention. A consequence of this is a “leaky” universe that would expand forever and suffer a “cold” death.

Fig. 4-(a) Expansion Rate of the Universe (after Busca, et al, ref.13, with permission), H , Hubble constant (km/sec/megaparsec), z , redshift; solid curve is predicted by Λ CDM model.
 (b) ---- schematic of change in internal energy, E (scale arbitrary), with time, t , years

Another interpretation of the change in slope of the dE/dt plot is to assert that the universe is closed and the expansion remains adiabatic. Thermodynamics then demands that for the accelerated expansion to continue, the Pressure, P , in equation (9) must be negative. This seems consistent with the negative Pressure associated with Dark Energy. However, it should be noted that this is not due to an anti-gravity effect but rather due to a thermodynamic requirement in order to maintain conservation of energy in a closed universe.

In our model, the acceleration can be viewed as an increase in flow velocity of matter-energy as the density decreases. Thus, if one takes a cross section of the universe at time t , the flow rate of mass-energy, m ($\text{kg}/\text{m}^2\text{-sec}$), is given by

$$m = \rho v \quad (10)$$

where ρ is the density (kg/m^3) and v (m/sec) is the flow velocity. As the density of matter-energy decreases (near $a= 0.65$) due to dominance of Dark Energy, the flow velocity increases, resulting in an acceleration in the expansion. of the universe. Such acceleration, however, cannot continue forever since the universe is closed. Gravity will eventually take over and cause the expansion to reverse. Both matter and space will shrink under the force of gravity and bring the universe back into its initial condition to begin a new cycle in what is dubbed a “cyclic universe”.

4. NATURE AND PROPERTIES OF SPACE QUANTA

Our quantum space theory suggests some characteristics of space quanta:

- 1). They differ from electromagnetic radiation, since they cannot be detected by spectroscopic techniques. The electromagnetic field is a vector field which carries charge while the space field does not and is a scalar field.
- 2). Space also differs from gravity. The space force is repulsive and opposite to that of gravity; which is an attractive force between material objects.
- 3). It may be that the space field is the “mother” field, from which arose both force fields and matter fields [12]. Recall that at the beginning that we postulated a quantum space era when there were only energy and space, from which were “born” radiation first and matter later.
- 4). The space waves (spaceons) propagate space and transport energy in the universe. Space also acts as the reservoir of energy in the universe. Virtual particles can pop in and out of space. When particles and antimatter annihilate, they disappear and the energy goes back to space. When stars and supernovas die and implode their energies go back to space.
- 5). Finally, it is interesting to note that in the limit of the size of space approaching zero ($\lambda =0$) one has a “hole” of infinite energy (similar to a singularity). Did our universe originate from a “hole” which is a gateway from another universe?

5. ON THE NATURE OF DARK MATTER

Finally, we say a few words about the other component of our invisible universe, dark matter; its known characteristics match well those of a component present in our Phase Diagram (Fig.1). Dark matter [17] comprises 84% of the total mass of matter in the universe. At present, it makes up 24% of the total mass-energy of the universe. It remains a mysterious, hypothetical form of matter.

Among properties that have been reported in the literature are:

- 1). it neither emits or absorbs electromagnetic radiation, hence it is difficult to study.
- 2). it moves without friction.
- 3). it can only be detected through its gravitational effects on the motion of galaxies.
- 4). it is spread over large areas, like a cloud, and forms a “halo” around galaxies and clusters; its density decreasing as one moves away from the center [18].
- 5). it is also found in filaments between galaxies and clusters [19]. It has been observed that ordinary matter traces the path of dark matter; this has been attributed to a strong interaction between ordinary matter and dark matter.

We proceed with the premise that all components of universe were formed during the cosmic evolution and would have left their footprints in the sands of time, e.g, the CMB. The phase diagram (Fig.1) shows that the major phases in the formation of the universe are dark

energy, ordinary matter (gasses, solids), and plasma. Any present-day component of the universe must originate from one of these phases. From the observed properties of dark matter, and known characteristics of plasma [20], it appears reasonable to make the assignment that dark matter corresponds to the plasma form of matter that existed during the photon epoch, just before recombination. At this time the universe was opaque due to scattering of all photons by free electrons and protons. The following facts support this contention:

1). WMAP data, mentioned earlier, show that dark matter constitutes the major component of the universe soon after the Big Bang. During this time, the universe consisted of a hot plasma of electrons, and ionized H and He. It was opaque and cannot emit or absorb light. This state persisted until about 380,000 years after the Big Bang at which time recombination took place and the universe became transparent.

2). Other characteristics of plasmas match exactly those of dark matter. Plasma, like dark matter, hangs around like a cosmic fog around galaxies and clusters, making it invisible and difficult to characterize.

3). That ordinary matter traces the path of dark matter can be explained by the fact that upon recombination of electrons and positive ions in the dark matter plasma, ordinary matter is formed; the plasma evaporates into H and He gasses. Thus ordinary matter follows the trail of dark matter.

4). Filamentation is a characteristic of plasmas; they move without friction, since the ions do not have attractive interaction and move collectively instead [20]. This lack of interaction also explains the origin of dark matter halos [18] that hover around galaxies.

5). The dark matter plasma scatters elastically and hence do not clump or “stick together” thus remaining diffuse, fluffy, and “halo-like”. Hence, galaxies cannot form directly from dark matter.

Moreover, plasma constitutes the major form of matter in the universe [20], most of it invisible. Dark matter being a plasma form of matter seems closer to reality than exotic particles, like WIMPS, MACHOS, etc. [21] whose existence have not been demonstrated. While admittedly, our designation of dark matter as a plasma form of matter is qualitative at the moment, experimental evidence supporting its validity has started to appear in the literature [22]. Energy exchange between the dark matter plasma and the surrounding hydrogen gas can certainly provide a mechanism for energy exchange between the two states of matter. This is consistent with (3) above.

6. QUANTUM SPACE MODEL AND THE BIG BANG

Our Quantum Space Model of space and cosmic evolution differs from the Big Bang model in a number of notable features:

1). It avoids the problem of singularity by starting with a finite dimension of space/energy.

2). It does not need an inflationary stage in order to have a universe which is uniform and isotropic.

3). The universe started with a hizz rather than a big bang; the latter being generally thought of, as matter and energy flying all over the place and by the idea that it occurred “everywhere and nowhere, at the same time” in the universe.

We follow the same timeline in the evolution of the universe as that of the Big Bang although our model suggests the universe started with space, energy and radiation without matter. The latter was produced later by nucleation and growth processes during cooling of the

universe. The details of these are as yet unknown but should involve the various forces in the creation of fundamental particles as established by investigations in the field of particle physics

Our physical model is easier to visualize than Einstein's geometrical-mathematical model. It is based on Newtonian gravity which regarded gravity as a force rather than a curvature in 4-dimensional space-time. A physico-chemical approach is useful in this regard. We identified Dark Energy as the energy of space and its expansion is easily understood as the propagation of space quanta, the spaceons.

Our model of nucleation and growth processes is consistent with the observed timeline in the appearance of nuclei, atoms, stars and galaxies in the universe. Atoms were formed around 4×10^5 years from which stars and then galaxies were formed starting around 4×10^8 years after the Big Bang. In the Big Bang model, they were all formed at the same time at the moment of the "bang".

Our model involves a finite, spherical universe which evolved in time. As the universe expands its surface curvature becomes more flat. The Big Bang is interpreted as an open, flat universe and implies space as infinite.

Finally, our model lends itself easily to a thermodynamic approach which is able to predict the fate of the universe.

6. CONCLUSION

A physico-chemical approach, using a quantum model of space and thermodynamics, appears useful in understanding the evolution and the composition of our dark universe. Dark energy is the energy of space and the component of the universe responsible for its expansion. It is associated with a scalar field, dubbed as Quintessence. Dark matter, on the other hand, is a plasma form of matter, similar to the state of the universe at the photon epoch, before recombination. It is the precursor in the formation of ordinary matter. Dark energy and dark matter are neither "dark" nor "mysterious", they are just invisible; one is transparent, while the other is opaque. Further work is necessary to better understand the nature and properties of the space quanta and its associated quantum field. We also need to understand plasma in space and dark matter halos, and develop tools to study them. Our model brings into question some long standing concepts in the physical sciences. The concept of vacuum appears outdated; the term "vacuum energy" should be more appropriately called "space energy". The concept of inflation also needs to be reexamined. It appears rather artificial and unnecessary. Finally, thermodynamics indicates that the acceleration in expansion of our universe maybe related to a non adiabatic process due to an influx of energy from the "outside" the universe. It will be destined to die a cold death if the accelerated expansion continues. It can also be that our universe remains "closed" and the expansion continues to be adiabatic with a negative pressure. In this case, the universe will continue to expand (and cool) until the force of gravity overcomes it. The universe will then start to contract and return to its initial state of a "hole". Thus our universe maybe a "bubble" arising from a "mother" universe [22] or at the beginning of a new cycle following a "big crunch" of a cyclic universe [23].

7. REFERENCES

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